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PROSPER

Jean Monnet Network

An Economy that Works for People: Empty Slogan or Substantive Policy Agenda for the EU?

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1. Introduction

The Jean Monnet Network PROSPER¹ was launched in January 2025 with a three-year mandate to conduct a wide-ranging debate on EU internal policy, specifically focused on the theme of “an Economy that Works for People.” But what exactly does this phrase mean? Is “an Economy that Works for People” merely an appealing slogan or does it also represent a significant policy agenda, and thereby the basis for a substantive programme of research for the PROSPER Network?

This Policy Brief makes the argument that an Economy that Works for People (EWP), as a general concept, does indeed provide a coherent framework for EU economic policy-making. The PROSPER Network defines EWP as an economy that first and foremost benefits ordinary European citizens in practical, concrete ways. It is closely associated with the idea of the “social market economy,” a centrist approach to political economy maintaining that there is no contradiction between a robust social policy and a competitive market economy. Moreover, it is in this

dual spirit that the PROSPER Network has been designed, as it is composed of experts both in market integration and social policy.² Bringing together these two approaches, the PROSPER Network is conducting a policy debate on how EU economic governance should be configured to achieve the twin goals of prosperity and social fairness.

This Policy Brief is structured as follows. It shows how the idea of EWP, as put forward by Ursula von der Leyen in 2019, is rooted in the concept of the social market economy (Part 2). Furthermore it demonstrates how this approach, combining the pursuit of both social fairness and prosperity, was given institutional expression in the structure and legislative programme of the European Commission of 2019-2024 (Part 3). Next, it identifies some practical examples how the EU has pursued a “people-centred” economic policy in the areas of technology, the social policy response to the pandemic, and the social economy (Part 4). Finally,

¹ The author is Research Coordinator of the Jean Monnet Network PROSPER (Project to Research Opportunities to Strengthen Prosperity and Economic Resilience in the EU), a multi-year EU-funded project (Grant No. 101176143), led by Dublin City University (Federico Fabbrini, Principal Investigator). See: <<https://prospernetwork.eu/>>. This publication reflects only the views of the author, and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

² The 12 Partner Institutions of the Jean Monnet Network PROSPER are Dublin City University (Coordinator), Pompeu Fabra University, University of Luxembourg, Université Paris-Est Créteil, Erasmus University Rotterdam, University of Copenhagen, Jagiellonian University Krakow, Free University of Bolzano/Bozen, Central European University, Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Université Libre de Bruxelles. <<https://prospernetwork.eu/partner-institutions/>>.

it concludes by reflecting on the uncertain future of EWP, given that competitiveness is now the overriding priority of EU economic policy (Part 5).

2. A (Social Market) Economy that Works for People

On the face of it, the idea of “an economy that works for people” is self-evident to the point of banality: who should an economy benefit, if not people? But the significance of EWP is that it makes a fundamental statement of values regarding the relationship between economy and society. The market does not exist apart from social institutions but is embedded within them.³ Workers are not mere factors of production but are also citizens participating in a democratic society; economic arrangements must enjoy popular support. In short, the purpose of the economy is to benefit society, not vice versa. These are the basic tenets of the social market economy.

In fact, when Ursula von der Leyen put forward EWP as one of the policy guidelines for the new Commission, she

framed it as an explicit affirmation of “our unique European social market economy.”⁴ This was presented as a centrist approach to political economy, striving for both “social fairness and prosperity” and rejecting the notion that there is a contradiction between the pursuit of these two goals. In this vein, she insisted with emphasis that “it is high time that we reconcile the *social* and the *market* in today’s modern economy.”⁵

The social market economy may be traced back to postwar (West) Germany, where – to greatly simplify a complex and contested concept – it was an economic model that offered a third way between laissez-faire capitalism and socialism.⁶ Initially this model applied only to the nation-state and not to the European level of governance, where the EEC/EU was becoming a highly integrated transnational market economy with little or no social dimension. Even as the EU eventually began to develop its own social policy, there continued to be a notable debate over whether the EU could ever truly be a social market economy.⁷

³ Caporaso, James A., and Sidney Tarrow. “Polanyi in Brussels: Supranational Institutions and the Transnational Embedding of Markets.” *International Organization* 63, no. 4 (2009): 593–620. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0020818309990099>.

⁴ Joerges, Christian, and Florian Rödl, *The ‘Social Market Economy’ as Europe’s Social Model?*, EUI LAW, 2004/08 - <https://hdl.handle.net/1814/2823>.

⁵ von der Leyen, U. 2019. *A Union that Strives for More. My Agenda for Europe. Political Guidelines for the Next European Commission 2019–2024*.

Strasbourg, p.8. Available at: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024_en.

⁶ *Ibid.*, p.9.

⁷ Fritz W. Scharpf, ‘The asymmetry of European integration, or why the EU cannot be a ‘social market economy’’, *Socio-Economic Review*, Volume 8, Issue 2, April 2010, Pages 211–250, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ser/mwp031>.

Amandine Crespy, ‘Can Scharpf Be Proved Wrong? Modelling the EU into a Competitive Social Market

An important milestone was reached when the Treaty of Lisbon (2007) enshrined the concept of the EU as a “highly competitive social market economy” (Art 3(3) TEU) – even if this treaty provision was largely aspirational. In the early 2010s, EU social policy progress stalled and even moved into reverse, as the institutions of EU economic governance were consumed with managing the Eurozone crisis, while often pressuring member states to impose austerity policies. It was only in the late 2010s that the EU took a significant solidaristic turn,⁸ most notably with the proclamation in November 2017 of the European Pillar of Social Rights (EPSR), a non-binding set of 20 key principles in the field of EU social policy. The EPSR directly prefigured the approach of the first von der Leyen Commission (2019-2024).

3. The Mixed Economic Approach of the 2019-2024 European Commission

The idea at the heart of the social market economy – that the twin goals of social fairness and prosperity should be pursued in tandem – was

embedded in the 2019-2024 Commission under the heading of EWP, built into its policy guidelines, organizational structure and legislative programme.

EWP was one of six policy guidelines (the others included “A European Green Deal”) set out by Ursula von der Leyen when she addressed the European Parliament (EP) as a candidate to lead the Commission in July 2019. It should be recalled that von der Leyen, a German EPP politician, was not a *Spitzenkandidat* in the 2019 election, but emerged afterwards as a surprise choice nominated by the European Council. The 2019 elections had produced a fractious EP where Eurosceptic populist parties had made large gains. In the circumstances, she needed to craft a message that would gain the support of the broad pro-EU majority in the EP – EPP, Renew, S&Ds and Greens – and EWP was part of her pitch.

The political guidelines reflected this mixed economic approach.⁹ Under the section with the heading EWP, the guidelines include proposals for efficient market regulation under sub-headings on “Supporting small

Economy for the next Generation,” European Law Journal 26, no. 5-6 (November 2020): 319-330 <https://doi.org/10.1111/eulj.12406>.

⁸ Ferrera, Maurizio, ‘The solidaristic turn in public opinion’, *Politics and Social Visions: Ideology, Conflict, and Solidarity in the EU* (Oxford, 2024), pp. 289–316.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198863304.003.0011>.

⁹ von der Leyen, U. 2019. *A Union that Strives for More. My Agenda for Europe. Political Guidelines for the Next European Commission 2019–2024*. Strasbourg, pp.8-12.

business” (including Capital Markets Union) and “Deepening our Economic and Monetary Union” (including Banking Union and Stability and Growth Pact reform), but also proposals to achieve social fairness and cohesion under sub-headings on “Europe’s Social pillar” (implementing the EPSR, including e.g. a “fair minimum wage”), “A Union of equality” (esp. gender equality in the workplace) and “Fair taxation” (reform of corporate taxation).

The mixed approach was also manifest in the quasi-hierarchical structure of the new Commission.¹⁰ Five Commission portfolios were grouped together under the heading of EWP, which covered areas both of economic policy (Economy, Trade, Financial Services) and of social policy (Jobs, Cohesion), all of which were within the authority of one lead Commissioner, “Executive Vice President for An Economy that Works for People” (Valdis Dombrovskis) with overall responsibility for economic and social policy.

Finally, the mixed approach was effectuated in a substantial legislative

programme, which brought together both market regulation and social policy measures under the single heading of EWP. This programme included the most important legislative measures related to the EU budget (including the Multiannual Financial Framework and the Next Generation EU Covid recovery programme), as well as economic regulation and social policy. Over the 5-year institutional cycle, EWP generated a substantial legislative programme, most of which was successfully adopted, according to end-of-term assessments.¹¹

4. “People-Centred” Economic Policy-Making?

We have noted that EWP, a concept closely related to the idea of the social market economy, can provide a coherent framework for EU economic policy-making. But to what extent can this general approach generate specific, actionable policy proposals? Does it make sense to talk about a “people-centred” economic policy, and if so, what would it look like? For the sake of debate, three kinds of EU policy initiatives may be briefly suggested as

¹⁰ Hans von der Burchard and Madi Winfield, “Ursula von der Leyen’s actual org chart,” Politico.eu., 11 September 2019.

<https://www.politico.eu/article/european-commission-president-elect-ursula-von-der-leyen-actual-organization-chart-commissioners-portfolios/>.

¹¹ Christoph Bierbrauer, “Priority 3: An Economy that works for People,” in *The von der Leyen Commission. Geopolitical Commission under the Pressure of*

Crises (2019-2024), Henrik Suder and Liska Wittenberg (eds.) (Baden-Baden: Nomos, 2024). Étienne Bassot “The six policy priorities of the von der Leyen Commission: An end-of-term assessment” European Parliament Research Service, April 2024.

[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/I/DAN/2024/762283/EPRS_IDA\(2024\)762283_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/I/DAN/2024/762283/EPRS_IDA(2024)762283_EN.pdf).

specific instances of such an approach – the regulation of technology, the social policy response to the pandemic, and the social economy.

First of all, the EU has notably taken a people-centred – or “human-centric”¹² – approach to the digital transformation. Technology threatens to displace people from economic progress in tangible ways: it may abridge human dignity, agency and autonomy in the workplace and the public sphere. Here are three examples: the working life of platform workers is increasingly governed by algorithms, without human oversight; the performance review of knowledge workers may be conducted by AI rather than a human being; and democracy itself is degraded when misinformation spreads unchecked on digital platforms. Some of the EU’s recent legislative initiatives in this field¹³ – namely the Platform Workers Directive,¹⁴ the AI Act,¹⁵ and the Digital Services Act¹⁶ – try to counter these

trends by restoring the place of people at the centre of economic policy-making.

Another recent example of people-centred economic policy – although one that is not well known – is the fact that a considerable portion of the EU pandemic response was focused on social policy. More than a quarter of the of the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) – around 28 % of the funds allocated (approximately €139.8 billion) – have been directed towards social objectives.¹⁷ Another more specific example is an action taken by the EU to avert mass unemployment at the height of the Covid-19 crisis. The EU devised a new programme, Support to mitigate Unemployment Risks in an Emergency (SURE), to backstop national short-time work schemes.¹⁸ This €100 billion temporary programme, the EU’s largest ever single intervention in the field of social policy, protected over 30 million workers from unemployment during the

¹² Celeste, E. (2025). “Digital Constitutionalism, EU Digital Sovereignty Ambitions and the Role of the European Declaration on Digital Rights.” In: Engel, A., Grousot, X., Petursson, G.T. (eds) *New Directions in Digitalisation. European Union and its Neighbours in a Globalized World*, vol 13. Springer, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-65381-0_13>.

¹³ It should be noted, however, that these three legislative initiatives technically fell under the rubric of “A Europe fit for the digital age,” and not “An economy that works for people.”

¹⁴ European Parliament, “Parliament Adopts Platform Work Directive,” 24 April 2024. <<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20240419IPR20584/parliament-adopts-platform-work-directive>>.

¹⁵ Marketa Pape, “Addressing AI risks in the workplace: Workers and algorithms.” European Parliament Research Service (June 2024).

<[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2024/762323/EPRS_BRI\(2024\)762323_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2024/762323/EPRS_BRI(2024)762323_EN.pdf)>.

¹⁶ See European Commission, The Digital Services Act, available at:

<https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/digital-services-act_en>.

¹⁷ Velina Lilyanova, “Social expenditure in the Recovery and Resilience Facility,” European Parliament Research Service, February 2024. <[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2024/757591/EPRS_BRI\(2024\)757591_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2024/757591/EPRS_BRI(2024)757591_EN.pdf)>.

¹⁸ Ian Cooper. 2024. *European Solidarity in Action: The SURE Programme between Fiscal Means and Social Ends*. REBUILD Working Paper No.19. <<https://zenodo.org/records/10671323>>.

pandemic. Whereas unemployment protection is a matter normally governed by member states, the EU acted out of necessity and solidarity to prevent a massive disruption to the lives of ordinary people.

A final example of people-centred policy-making is the encouragement of policies to foster the “social economy” – a catch-all term that includes cooperatives, charities, foundations, and social enterprise.¹⁹ The EU has developed an Action Plan for the Social Economy²⁰ that aims to foster this sector, which prioritizes environmental and social goals over the pursuit of profit.

5. Conclusion

Since 2019, EU economic policy-making has been framed with reference to the idea of promoting “an economy that works for people.” This term was the watchword of the first von der Leyen Commission (2019-2024), and it remained a consistent goal even as the EU was shaken by several momentous events that followed in quick succession: Brexit and its aftermath, the Covid-19 pandemic, and

the full-scale Russia-Ukraine War. However, there is some question as to whether the new Commission which took office in 2024 remains as committed to this goal. The overall political makeup of the Commission has shifted to the right, following a concomitant shift in the European Parliament following the 2024 elections. Whereas the previous Commission followed a mixed economic approach pursuing the twin goals of social fairness and prosperity – in line with the classic philosophy of the social market economy – the new Commission has embraced a single-minded focus on the pursuit of competitiveness, as is manifest in its new Competitiveness Compass.²¹ At this stage, it is too soon to tell how the EU economic policy will evolve. Yet there is no doubt that this crucial question, regarding the future economic policy of the EU, will continue to be the subject of intense research and policy debate within the PROSPER Jean Monnet Network in the years to come.

¹⁹ Forde, Andrew. “Consolidating Ireland’s Indigenous Social Enterprise Sector – A Policy Perspective” *The Irish Journal of Management*, vol. 41, no. 2, Sciendo, 2022, pp. 93-102. <https://doi.org/10.2478/ijm-2023-0003>.

²⁰ European Commission, *Building an economy that works for people: an action plan for the social economy*, December 2021. [https://www.socialeconomy.eu.org/wp-](https://www.socialeconomy.eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Building-an-economy-that-works-for-people-an-action-plan-for-the-social-economy.pdf)

[content/uploads/2021/12/Building-an-economy-that-works-for-people-an-action-plan-for-the-social-economy.pdf](https://www.socialeconomy.eu.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/Building-an-economy-that-works-for-people-an-action-plan-for-the-social-economy.pdf).

²¹ European Commission, *A Competitiveness Compass for the EU*. 29 January 2025. https://commission.europa.eu/document/download/10017eb1-4722-4333-add2-e0ed18105a34_en?filename=Communication_1.pdf.

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